

EFFECT OF ADVERTISING EXPENSES ON SALES INCREASE

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Introduction

Historically, businesses exploited their creativity in full in order to establish various ways to attract their product users; one initiated way was investing into advertisement, expecting an advertised product to be purchased by consumers more often (Kumar & Raju, 2013). Many scholars have spent years investigating the relationship between advertising expenses and sales growth, eventually, coming to various results; however, one major pillar of agreement was on identifying the relationship of the advertiser to the sales effort (Akanbi & Adeyeye, 2011) and direct link of advertisement with sales of the product (Adekoya, 2011). Indeed, investment into advertisement is associated with sales increase, but still, Nkrumah, Adu-Twum, Buabeng, & Charway (2018); Kumar & Raju (2013); and others have claimed that increased sales are not the sole purpose of advertising. Companies spend huge amounts of money on advertisement in order to enlarge market share (Nkrumah, Adu-Twum, Buabeng, & Charway, 2018), to gain brand awareness (Löfgren & Li, 2010; Akanbi & Adeyeye, 2011) and preference (Nkrumah, Adu-Twum, Buabeng, & Charway, 2018), and to cause purchase decision (Kumar & Raju, 2013; Ayanwale, Alimi, & Ayanbimipe, 2005). While advertising expenses may be advocated by several objectives identified previously, “business executors want to know, how advertising has contributed to sales and ultimately to the company’s bottom line?” (Akanbi & Adeyeye, 2011).

Statement of the Problem

Today, advertisers incur huge expenditures to diligently keep individuals (market) interested in their produced goods or services (Ayanwale, Alimi, & Ayanbimipe, 2005; Löfgren & Li, 2010; Nkrumah, Adu-Twum, Buabeng, & Charway, 2018) aiming for company failing risk minimization (Lukason & Hoffman, 2014), however, still most companies go bankrupt even despite extensive advertising expenses on their products.

Research Question

So far the literature has indicated that the main outcome of the studies conducted was a definite relationship between advertising expenses and sales volume (Adekoya, 2011; Akanbi & Adeyeye, 2011; Ayanwale, Alimi, & Ayanbimipe, 2005; Kumar & Raju, 2013). Accordingly, the main research question we might address is to identify if extensive advertising expenses have a significant impact on sales increase and profitability of the firm.

Research Objectives

Based on the research question, the general aim of this paper is to examine a particular correlation between investment into advertisement and proportional sales growth that results in a successful business performance. So, the broken-down research objectives are to reveal whether advertising is solely responsible for business success or bankruptcy; to evaluate measures of advertising expenses and corresponding sales growth; to establish ways to decrease advertising expenditures and still maintain profitability by means of management decisions or marketing tools.

Literature Review

This section of the paper looks at research studies that were conducted with regard to variables related to advertising, brand affiliation, and bankruptcy. It investigates the literature related to the following study by assessing the relationships of these variables, the authors and their major findings.

Forms of Advertisement

Based on the literature, advertisement usually comes in two forms, broadcast (audio-visual) and print advertisement (non-audio-visual). Audio-visual advertisement comprises transmission channels such as television, radio, and emerging media (internet). Non-audio-visual advertisement is conveyed through means of newspapers and magazines.

Ayanwale, Alimi, & Ayanbimipe (2005) in their study aimed at examination of the role advertising plays in impacting consumers brand preference based on the case study of Cadbury Nigeria PLC. The research approach they used was quantitative; the population considered Nigerian citizens while the sample size included 350 respondents using a random sampling technique. Data was collected by means of a structured questionnaire and analyzed using percentage analysis and Chi-Square based on the variables like consumer brand preference, media preference awareness sources, gender, and age group. As a result of this research, television under the audio-visual form of advertisement was noted as the most potent of all media to influence customers to choose one brand to another. While another study of Nkrumah, Adu-Twum, Buabeng, & Charway (2018) has also revealed that more than 50% of survey respondents indicated TV advertisement to be the most influential medium towards consumer brand preference. This finding was based on the quantitative research technique adopted in the study with a sample size of 399 respondents based in La Nkwantanang Municipality, Ghana. A close-ended questionnaire was used on the subject of sachet water.

This tendency is significant to observe as the time difference between two studies is 13 years. Despite this time difference, TV advertisement has maintained its domination among all media due to its audio-visual appealing effect on consumers (Nkrumah, Adu-Twum, Buabeng, & Charway, 2018).

Advertisement Objectives

The reasons behind marketing promotion of businesses through advertisement can be divided into the following categories based on the literature:

- Sales Volume Increase

- Raising Brand Preference

- Promoting Brand Loyalty

-Affecting Consumer Decision Making

Advertising and Sales Volume

The role of advertising on sales volume has been an important matter because what is purchased often times is based on what has been heard or practically used (Adekoya, 2011). The author of one of the studies, Adekoya (2011), in his paper aimed to assess how advertising could possibly influence the sales growth of a product and how this sales volume could help the company keep going in business. In order to achieve the objectives of the research, Adekoya (2011) has collected data using primary and secondary sources. The primary source was a questionnaire handed out to the company workers; data driven from this questionnaire was interpreted and analyzed using various tables such as tables of comparison, effect and impact tables, buying attitude and selection tables, which were measured by frequencies and percentages. Outcomes of the thoroughly conducted analysis were significant findings such as that advertising not only facilitates maintenance of superior stand in the industry and profit maximization but also enhances promotion of products, services, and ideas (Adekoya, 2011). Most importantly, Adekoya (2011) states that no matter how successful the product is, advertising is always a must and should be a continuing activity.

Additionally, another study conducted by Akanbi & Adeyeye (2011) has similarly aimed at revealing the effect of product advertising on its sales volume, increased market share and profitability. The relationship between advertising and sales was summarized and presented as The Concave Downward Function and The S-Shaped Response Function. Data analysis of the secondary sources driven from the company's annual reports and accounts as well as linear regression with use of ordinary least square has led Akanbi & Adeyeye (2011) to the conclusion that confirmed that a positive and significant relationship existed between advertising and sales.

Advertising and Brand Preference

Another intended result of advertising efforts is brand preference. Thus, Ayanwale, Alimi, & Ayanbimipe (2005) in their study aimed at revealing the cause effect relationship between advertisement and brand affiliation. The authors were able to retrieve significant respondent characteristics from data interpretation and analysis such as gender neutrality in the consumption of the observed products, dominance of youths in the market for the products of the given company, Advertising and Quality difference which made up about 90% of the reason for the observed brand preference. The major findings of this study are that advertising helps in projecting product quality and value before the consumers while consumers regardless their age or gender are equally influenced by advertising in their preference for the brand (Ayanwale, Alimi, & Ayanbimipe, 2005).

Alternatively, another study conducted by Nkrumah, Adu-Twum, Buabeng, & Charway (2018) aimed at the related variables applied in their study to look at the influence of advertisement on brand preference of customers. Conversely, this study has pointed out that advertising has a weak positive effect on consumer brand preference; it raises awareness about the product rather than stimulating a final action (Nkrumah, Adu-Twum, Buabeng, & Charway, 2018).

Advertising and Brand Loyalty

Another approach for assessing advertising expenses and effects was relating advertisement and brand loyalty. Löfgren & Li (2010) have conducted a research, indicated purpose of which was establishing how much effect celebrity endorsement in advertisements has on brand loyalty. Sufficient amount of data was collected and analyzed by the authors such as questionnaire, research reports and magazines in order to address the main research question. Marketers have been using celebrity endorsement as a marketing tool which they believed successfully assisted in improvement of brand awareness, brand equity, and even financial returns (Löfgren & Li, 2010). However, after careful data observation, Löfgren & Li (2010) ended up with quite an opposite result - neither brand

loyalty nor attitudinal loyalty is confirmed to be created by famous endorsers. It is regarded as a result of somewhat overlooking the brand loyalty making a stress only on behavioral aspect once it consists of both attitudinal and behavioral aspects (Löfgren & Li, 2010).

Advertising and Consumer Decision Making

Consumers are more likely to have a decisional response toward brands that promote emotional messages and values through their advertisements (Kumar & Raju, 2013). Thus, scholars Kumar & Raju (2013) have researched the topic of advertising and consumer decision making processes based on psychological appeal of ads to males and females. Their study objective was to assess effect of advertising on customer buying behavior. In order to address the objective of the study, Kumar & Raju (2013) have collected primary and secondary data for further assessment and analysis. For obtaining primary source data, the authors have implemented a structured questionnaire. Data received through the questionnaire was properly analyzed and interpreted with the help of tools like Chi-Square, Likert Scale, frequencies and cross tabulation. The major findings Kumar & Raju (2013) have encountered are that advertisement is able to change consumer's perception about the given product and consumers are hugely exposed to the brand advertisements that provide sought-for information about the brands.

According to the listed and reviewed literature, the theoretical gap lays within the relationship of advertisement and bankruptcy variables. This aspect is going to be covered and investigated within this study.

Bankruptcy Causes

In order to assess the relationship between advertising expenditures and going bankrupt, the causes of business failure should be defined properly. The study of Lukason & Hoffman (2014) performed a tremendous work to look for and establish relevant possible causes. The data regarding bankruptcy causes was derived from the primary source – court judgements of manufacturing firms. The authors

have predominantly divided the causes to two taxonomies, management deficiencies and external factors (Lukason & Hoffman, 2014). Bankruptcy scores that indicate failure risks were calculated basing on Ohlson's model and Grunberg's bankruptcy prediction model. In order to examine if different causes relate to corresponding failure risks, independent samples median tests were applied. According to Lukason & Hoffman (2014), an important finding of the study was that suddenly failing firms are characterized by a failure cause from a single environment, either internal or external, meanwhile firms that go bankrupt gradually are associated with failure causes originating from both environments. Deepening into the topic of bankruptcy, additional research was conducted by Jindal & McAlister (2015) to attain the objective of reducing bankruptcy risk. It has indicated that bankruptcy prediction performance has improved when marketing variables were included in addition to the usual financial predictors (Jindal & McAlister, 2015). The major findings of the research are that market stability increases impact of advertising assets on reducing bankruptcy risk, whereas market turbulence increases the impact of R&D assets on reducing bankruptcy risk (Jindal & McAlister, 2015). Another research conducted by Jindal (2020) has looked into how advertsing and Research & Development benefit firms by raising sales and sharholder value. On the other hand, the outcome of the study reveals that when in bankruptcy, these variables could actually appear as a double-edged sword in terms of (Jindal, 2020). Additionally, out-of-sample validation indicates prediction of whether a firm will survive bankruptcy is significantly improved by considering advertising and R&D (Jindal, 2020).

Methodology

This section of the paper focuses on presenting the research methodology and justification of corresponding choices. It reveals the research design, sampling of the study, data collection, data description and data analysis procedures.

Research Design

To establish the relationship between the independent variable, advertisement, and dependent variable, business performance (successful or poor), the quantitative research approach was applied. This approach enabled to gather statistical numeric data to implement a cause-effect analysis of these two variables. The research design is descriptive to simpler define an actual information needed from participants.

Population and Sampling

Target Population

This study focused on 657,277 residents of Bishkek city (*National Statistical Committee of the Kyrgyz Republic, 2020*). It comprised both male and female residents aged from 18 and above as this age group represents people who are the most capable of making thoughtful and objective purchase decisions.

Sample Size

The sample size for this research was 400 respondents from Bishkek both male and female of age from 18 and above. This sample size was obtained using the formula of Taro Yamane:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

n – sample size

N – population size

e – acceptable sampling error (5%)

95% Confidence level is assumed

$$n = \frac{657277}{1+657277(0.05)^2}$$

n = 400

Sampling Techniques

Non-probability sampling technique was used because the individuals were not selected on a random basis. In order to ensure that respondents would be giving accurate and reliable information, convenience sampling technique was adopted to survey people who are willing to and available to contribute to the study.

Data Collection

In order to have a holistic view for such a wide coverage, the primary source was used for this study. The main data collection instrument for a primary source was a questionnaire. This questionnaire was a structured self-administered survey which was distributed among the sample size. It comprised close-ended questions within four sections. The first section was a profile of a respondent, the second section focused on the forms of advertisement. The third section aimed at collecting quantitative data on factors of sales volume increase while the fourth one comprised Likert Scale with options including Non-Influential, Less Influential, Neutral, Influential, Very Influential.

Data Analysis

To analyze the data collected, descriptive and inferential statistics were used. Responses from the questionnaire were summarized by frequencies and percentages. To analyze the association between advertisement and sales volume, correlation and regression were used. The dependent variable, sales volume (Y) was correlated and regressed against the independent variable, advertisement (X). The correlation was used to investigate the relationship between these two variables while the regression was used to define the strength of this relationship. If $R > 0.50$, it points to a strong positive relationship between independent and dependent variables. If $R < 0.50$, it points to a weak positive relationship between independent and dependent variables.

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